

Enhancing Maritime Situational Awareness through Adaptive Mobile Multi-Sensor Platforms

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Abstract—Maritime critical infrastructures are increasingly exposed to hybrid cyber-physical threats, including GNSS spoofing, AIS manipulation, and the use of unmanned systems. However, existing surveillance approaches predominantly rely on static sensor installations and often focus on isolated or limited data sources, hindering their ability to provide comprehensive situational awareness.

In this paper, we are introducing an adaptive, mobile multi-sensor network for real-time maritime surveillance that enables the generation of cyber-physical situational pictures through the fusion of heterogeneous data sources. The system combines deployable land-based multi-sensor platforms (“Cells on Wheels”) with a sensor-equipped research vessel, allowing flexible and on-demand data acquisition in diverse operational environments. We describe the overall system architecture, report on initial deployment experiences and derive key lessons learned regarding system integration, data quality, and operational constraints in real-world scenarios. Our results highlight the potential of mobile sensing approaches to complement existing maritime surveillance systems and improve the resilience of critical infrastructures through adaptive and scalable monitoring capabilities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime situational awareness is a critical capability for ensuring safety, security, and the efficient operation of coastal and port environments. Factors such as increasing traffic density, the protection of critical maritime infrastructure, and the necessity of detecting anomalous or hazardous behaviors demand comprehensive and reliable monitoring solutions [1]. Traditional systems, including fixed radar installations and Automatic Identification System (AIS) networks, provide essential data but are frequently constrained by coverage gaps, rigid infrastructure dependencies, and limited operational flexibility [2]–[4].

To address these limitations, research has increasingly focused on the integration of heterogeneous data sources and advanced analytics to enhance maritime awareness [1], [5]. In particular, multi-sensor data fusion approaches combining AIS, radar, and additional sensing modalities have demonstrated significant improvements in vessel tracking accuracy and anomaly detection capabilities [6]–[8]. At the same time, the growing relevance of cyber-physical threats, such as AIS spoofing or Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) interference, has further emphasized the need for more adaptive and resilient monitoring architectures [9]–[11].

Distributed sensing architectures and mobile platforms offer a versatile means of augmenting these legacy systems. Specifically, mobile multi-sensor platforms facilitate rapid deployment and adaptive coverage through the integration of heterogeneous data sources, such as radar, AIS, electro-optical sensors, and radio frequency (RF) measurements. Systems such as the TRAILER platform [12] or the multi-sensor platform introduced by [13] demonstrate the feasibility of mobile, cooperative sensing infrastructures for maritime environments, enabling flexible data acquisition and improved situational awareness in dynamic scenarios. These approaches are particularly advantageous in temporary operations, dynamic threat scenarios, or remote areas where permanent infrastructure is insufficient or non-existent [14].

This paper presents a mobile, multi-sensor approach for maritime monitoring centered on deployable multi-sensor platforms. The system integrates diverse sensing modalities with flexible communication and processing capabilities to generate a cohesive situational picture in real-world environments. Throughout this work, particular emphasis is placed on practical deployment, cross-system integration, and operational experience.

The main contribution of this work is the evaluation of the proposed system in real-world maritime deployments, including both coastal and port environments. The paper provides insights into system performance, identifies key technical and operational challenges, and derives lessons learned for the design and deployment of mobile multi-sensor platforms.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the mobile multi-sensor platforms and describes the overall system design and components, while Section 3 presents deployment results and lessons learned.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW: MOBILE MULTI-SENSOR NETWORK

The proposed system is designed as a modular and mobile multi-sensor network to enable adaptive maritime surveillance in dynamic operational environments. In contrast to conventional monitoring approaches that rely on fixed sensor infrastructures, the presented concept allows the on-demand deployment of sensing capabilities to areas of interest [13], [14]. This flexibility is particularly relevant in the context of

Fig. 1. CoW during operation (left), CoW in transport set-up (top right), research vessel "Vektor" (bottom right).

maritime critical infrastructure protection, where threat scenarios may evolve rapidly and require temporary or relocatable monitoring solutions. The overall objective of the system is to provide a comprehensive and coherent situational picture by combining heterogeneous observations from multiple domains. Rather than focusing on a single sensing modality, the system integrates complementary data sources to improve coverage, robustness, and interpretability of the observed maritime environment.

A. Mobile Multi-Sensor Platforms

The physical layer of the system consists of multiple mobile multi-sensor platforms, including deployable land-based units and a sensor-equipped research vessel. The land-based platforms are implemented as so-called "Cells on Wheels" (CoWs), which can be rapidly transported and deployed in coastal or port environments. Each unit is equipped with a telescopic mast for sensor mounting, an onboard power supply, and communication interfaces. The design enables setup times within one hour, making the platforms suitable for temporary monitoring tasks, event-based deployments, or rapid response scenarios.

Complementing the land-based units, a research vessel equipped with additional sensing capabilities provides an off-shore perspective. This platform enables data collection directly from the water and allows measurements that are not feasible from shore-based locations alone. The combination of land-based and maritime platforms results in complementary observation geometries and improved spatial coverage. Furthermore, the use of multiple platforms in the same coverage area introduces redundancy and increases resilience against individual sensor failures or environmental limitations. This is particularly relevant in operational scenarios where continuous monitoring is required despite changing conditions. Figure 1 shows the research vessel and CoWs in operation and transport set-up.

The system's development is guided by four primary architectural objectives:

- Mobility and rapid deployability, enabling flexible positioning of multi-sensor platforms in response to emerging situations
- Modularity, allowing the integration of different sensor types and platform configurations
- Scalability, supporting deployments ranging from small setups to larger distributed networks
- Robustness, achieved through redundancy and complementary sensing perspectives

The system integrates a diverse set of sensors to capture different aspects of the maritime environment. Core data sources include:

- AIS for vessel tracking
- VHF radio monitoring and direction finding (DF) for receiving maritime communication and estimating signal direction
- GNSS monitoring for assessing positioning integrity
- Automatic Dependent Surveillance–Broadcast (ADS-B) for observing aerial traffic
- Electro-optical cameras for visual observation and verification
- Radar systems for independent detection and tracking of vessels

B. Network Architecture and Data Flow

The system architecture is based on a distributed sensing paradigm utilizing a hybrid processing model. This architecture is anchored by a centralized coordination layer, which is complemented by decentralized edge processing to ensure operational resilience.

Primary data processing occurs within a centralized data platform, which serves as the system's core analytical engine. All sensor streams from the multi-sensor platforms are aggregated and stored here, providing a unified environment for high-level data fusion. Beyond fused outputs, raw data streams can be accessed. This dual-access model allows consumer services — such as visualization dashboards or anomaly detection — to utilize both historical archives and live telemetry. Figure 2 depicts the data flow and concept of the data platform and sensor network.

This centralized approach is essential for:

- **Consistent Data Access:** Providing a "single source of truth" for operators and analytical components.
- **Cross-Platform Correlation:** Enabling the fusion of heterogeneous data (e.g., AIS, radar and camera data) to address various use cases.
- **Scalable Analytics:** Leveraging high-performance computing resources for AI-based analysis that would exceed the capacity of individual sensor nodes.

To enhance system robustness, the architecture integrates optional decentralized edge processing. Each sensor platform functions as an autonomous unit capable of independent data acquisition and communication. When equipped with an

Fig. 2. Concept and data flow of mobile platforms and data platform.

edge computing module, a platform can perform localized processing of its own sensor data. This capability serves as a fail-safe mechanism, allowing for continued operation during connectivity loss and providing a localized, offline-capable situational picture.

Data collected by the multi-sensor platforms is transmitted to a central processing infrastructure via wireless communication links. Depending on the deployment scenario, this includes cellular networks such as LTE or 5G, enabling flexible operation without dedicated communication infrastructure. Data streams are transmitted securely using different technologies, i.e. Kafka and tcp streams, over a WireGuard VPN tunnel.

Furthermore, the system is designed for extensibility; the data platform utilizes standardized interfaces to ingest data from supplementary sources, including external APIs, third-party sensor systems, and existing stationary infrastructure. This ensures that the situational picture can be enriched with a broader range of environmental and maritime data without requiring significant architectural modifications.

C. Advantages of Mobility

Mobility represents a key differentiating feature of the proposed approach. By enabling rapid deployment and repositioning of sensor platforms, the system supports adaptive monitoring strategies tailored to specific operational needs. For example, temporary surveillance zones can be established in response to emerging threat situations, large-scale events, or incidents affecting critical infrastructure.

Compared to permanently installed systems, mobile platforms offer a cost-effective and flexible alternative, particularly in areas where long-term infrastructure deployment is not feasible. Mobile sensing has been identified as a key enabler for flexible and resilient monitoring in large-scale environments [5], [13].

In addition, dynamic sensor placement allows improved spatial coverage and enables the system to address gaps or blind spots in existing monitoring networks. This capability is especially important in heterogeneous maritime environments with complex geographical and infrastructural conditions.

D. Example Use Cases

The data captured by the mobile multi-sensor platforms can be leveraged for several advanced, data-driven applications that enhance the maritime situational picture. For example:

- **Cross-Modal Verification and Anomaly Detection:** By fusing AIS (self-reported) data with independent radar detections and VHF direction finding, the system can identify "dark vessels" or instances of AIS manipulation where physical signal bearings diverge from reported positions [2], [15], [16].
- **GNSS Integrity Monitoring:** Long-term analysis of GNSS signal data allows for the detection of regional interference, such as GNSS spoofing or jamming, ensuring the reliability of positioning data for critical maritime infrastructure [11].
- **Radio Frequency (RF) Fingerprinting:** Data from VHF radio monitoring and direction finding can be used to categorize unique signal characteristics, helping to identify specific transmitters and estimate signal directions even when identity data is missing [17].
- **Automated Target Classification:** High-resolution streams from electro-optical cameras and radar can be processed via AI-based analysis to automatically classify vessel types and verify the intent of maritime traffic in real-time [1].
- **Multi-Domain Traffic Correlation:** Integrating ADS-B aerial data with surface maritime sensors enables the correlation of coordinated activities between drones and vessels, providing a comprehensive cyber-physical situational picture across different domains [8].

III. DEPLOYMENT AND LESSONS LEARNED

To assess the feasibility and practical applicability of the proposed mobile multi-sensor network, two deployment campaigns were conducted in real-world maritime environments. These deployments evaluated both the technical performance of the system and its operational suitability. This section summarizes the deployment setup, identifies technical and operational challenges, and synthesizes key lessons learned for future iterations.

A. Deployment Setup and Operational Scenarios

The system was deployed in two representative maritime environments: a coastal area (Kieler Förde) and a major port area (Hamburger Hafen), each for multiple weeks between October 2025 and March 2026. Continuous data collection under varying environmental and traffic conditions enabled comprehensive evaluation. The campaigns aimed primarily to test data acquisition and processing workflows, as well as to gain operational experience with the platforms.

The setup time for each platform was typically less than one hour, demonstrating the system's rapid deployability. Communication between distributed nodes and the central processing infrastructure was established via 4G cellular connections using dedicated GSM antennas. Data from AIS, ADS-B, radar, VHF reception (including direction finding) and weather data

was continuously recorded and analyzed to evaluate system performance and operational reliability.

B. Technical Challenges and Analysis

Data quality and cross-validation: Data quality and reception were generally reliable across sensors. AIS, ADS-B, radar, and weather data streams remained stable, and no major availability issues occurred. The main challenge involved cross-validation between platforms. In several instances, platforms reported conflicting observations, particularly for VHF reception and direction finding, where estimated bearings occasionally diverged. This highlights the need for mechanisms to assess observation reliability and establish confidence in multi-platform data. Especially, VHF reception and direction finding were influenced by reflections and multipath propagation, while radar and camera performance depended on weather conditions and line-of-sight constraints.

Temporal alignment: Temporal alignment of data streams was only a minor concern. GNSS-based time synchronization provided sufficient consistency, and small deviations in timestamps or latency did not impact overall performance.

Connectivity: Connectivity was not a limiting factor. The 4G setup provided reliable, high-bandwidth links for continuous transmission without significant data loss.

System integration effort: The most significant technical effort was in the initial orchestration and integration of heterogeneous data streams. Establishing and monitoring data pipelines, harmonizing interfaces, and ensuring consistent formats required substantial manual work. This underscores that while runtime operation is stable, system integration remains a critical and resource-intensive phase [6], [14].

C. Operational Considerations

Beyond technical metrics, the physical deployment revealed practical constraints that significantly impact system utility. A primary concern is site selection, where achieving optimal spatial coverage requires a balancing of line-of-sight requirements against the availability of secure terrain and surrounding infrastructure. Furthermore, ensuring a continuous and stable power supply for mobile platforms in remote or temporary scenarios remains a persistent challenge. Future iterations could include the integration of renewable energy solutions, such as solar-panels, to maintain operational autonomy. Additionally, the deployment of high-value sensor equipment in public-access port areas introduces risks related to equipment integrity. This necessitates the implementation of both stringent physical security measures and comprehensive remote health monitoring systems to detect and prevent unauthorized tampering or theft.

D. Synthesis of Lessons Learned

The conducted deployments provided several important insights into the design and operation of mobile multi-sensor networks. Mobility significantly enhances flexibility and enables adaptive monitoring strategies, yet it introduces additional complexity in terms of planning and coordination.

Effective deployment requires careful consideration of sensor placement, coverage objectives, and environmental constraints. Furthermore, the performance of data fusion is highly dependent on the quality of the underlying data. In practice, imperfect data must be expected, making robust preprocessing and validation mechanisms essential. Redundancy across multiple sensors proved to be a valuable strategy for mitigating data gaps and increasing overall system reliability. Real-world environments also introduce a level of variability difficult to replicate in controlled settings. This variability affects both sensor measurements and system behavior, emphasizing the importance of field testing and iterative refinement.

The spatial coverage of the system is inherently constrained by the number and placement of deployed platforms, and full-area monitoring may require a larger network of sensors. Additionally, the reliance on external communication infrastructure can limit performance in areas with poor connectivity. Furthermore, trade-offs between real-time processing and data completeness must be carefully managed depending on operational requirements. Future work will therefore focus on enhancing system scalability, improving data fusion and analysis methods, and increasing the level of automation in deployment and operation. The integration of additional sensor types and the expansion of edge processing capabilities to reduce bandwidth requirements are also considered promising directions for further development.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an adaptive, mobile multi-sensor network designed to enhance maritime situational awareness by addressing the limitations of static surveillance infrastructure. Through the integration of land-based "Cells on Wheels" and a sensor-equipped research vessel, the system demonstrated its ability to generate a cohesive situational picture using heterogeneous data sources like AIS, radar, and VHF direction finding. Real-world deployments in Kieler Förde and Hamburger Hafen validated the system's rapid deployability and robust data acquisition. While the results highlight the potential for improved resilience and spatial coverage, the campaigns also identified critical challenges, including the need for robust data cross-validation, system integration and site selection.

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